

1 **Novel gluten-free pasta made with purple corn: nutritional, technological and**
2 **sensorial quality**

3 Gonzalo Delgado-Pando^a, Marco Acerbo^a, Tatiana Pintado^a, Sonia de Pascual-Teresa^{a*}

4 ^aInstituto de Ciencia y Tecnología de Alimentos y Nutrición (ICTAN), CSIC, C/José

5 Antonio Novais 6, 28040, Madrid (Spain)

6 * Corresponding author. s.depascualteresa@csic.es

7 **Abstract**

8 Gluten-free products, including pasta, are generally highly processed and low in antioxidant
9 compounds, often with compromised organoleptic qualities. To address these limitations, we
10 designed a new gluten-free pasta based on purple corn, which is a variety rich in antioxidant
11 polyphenols. We developed five pasta variations—100% wheat semolina, 100% yellow corn,
12 90% yellow corn+10% rice flour, 100% purple corn, and 90% purple corn+10% rice flour —and
13 analyzed their chemical composition (particularly polyphenol content) as well as their physical,
14 technological, and sensory properties following extrusion and boiling. Extrusion proved effective
15 for corn pasta production, preserving polyphenol content and yielding good physical and
16 technological properties, whereas boiling reduced polyphenol levels by up to 80%. Sensometric
17 analysis indicated some unwanted attributes associated with purple corn. Overall, purple corn
18 pasta shows potential as a gluten-free alternative, rich in antioxidants and moderately resilient
19 to production and cooking processes, though sensory attributes may require further
20 optimization for higher consumer acceptance.

21

22 **Keywords:** purple corn, polyphenol, pasta, gluten free, anthocyanin, texture, sensorial

23 1. Introduction

24 Pasta products, widely consumed all over the world, play an important role in human nutrition
25 thanks to their convenience, moderate cost, good nutritional profile and versatility (Giacco et
26 al., 2016). Traditionally, pasta is produced with durum wheat semolina, a gluten containing
27 cereal belonging to the family *Triticum durum* (Murray et al., 2017). Gluten is a protein that
28 directly affects the structure of the pasta and its quality, including elasticity and tenacity (Zou et
29 al., 2016). Nevertheless, gluten negatively affects some individuals due to its protein fractions
30 that triggers an immune response in the small intestine, causing damage to the intestinal villi
31 and symptoms like diarrhea, bloating, and nutrient deficiencies (Husby et al., 2012). This
32 condition is known as celiac disease (CD) whose prevalence is estimated to affect approximately
33 1% of the population varying by sex, age and location (King et al., 2020). The increasing
34 prevalence of CD and gluten sensitivity has stimulated significant research into the development
35 of gluten-free alternatives to traditional wheat-based products (Gao et al., 2018).

36 Among the cereals used for GF foods production, corn and rice emerge as popular basic
37 ingredients for GF pasta (Giménez et al., 2012). Rice (*Oryza sativa*), due to its neutral color, easy
38 digestion, and hypoallergenic properties, is also a preferred grain for gluten-free foods.
39 Moreover, with its high amylose content, supports pasta structure through retrogradation,
40 enhancing firmness and texture (Marti et al., 2010). Corn (*Zea mays L.*) and cornstarch are
41 commonly used in gluten-free food preparation, often with xanthan gum addition (Zannini et al.,
42 2012) due to its positive effect on consistency, cooking quality, texture, and sensory acceptance
43 (Culetu et al., 2021). More often blends of various flours and additives are used to achieve the
44 desired quality for both production processes and consumer preferences in GF products (Marti
45 & Pagani, 2013).

46 Additionally, polyphenols can be a good ally for celiac people, because as reported by Calabrisio
47 et al. (2022), these substances indirectly mitigate gluten's harmful effects by helping strengthen

48 intestinal barriers, initiating a process that detoxifies gluten and reduces its absorption, thereby
49 protecting intestinal villi from degradation. Polyphenols are a class of natural compounds
50 derived from the secondary metabolism of plants and contribute to the maintenance and
51 protection of cells avoiding excessive oxidative stress and the onset of chronic diseases (Del Rio
52 et al., 2013). Although whole wheat products are a great source of phenolic acids, refined
53 products might lose these compounds (Nicoletti et al., 2013). However, many GF cereals are
54 rich in polyphenolic compounds, such as corn, buckwheat, quinoa, amaranth, red sorghum and
55 teff (Rolandelli et al., 2023; Verardo et al., 2011). Among them, colored corn stands out as an
56 excellent source of polyphenols and in the case of purple corn, especially in anthocyanin when
57 compared to the white and yellow analogues (Blanch et al., 2023; Pascual-Teresa et al., 2002).

58 The aim of this study was to formulate a gluten free pasta made with purple corn flour, not yet
59 existing in the market, evaluating two different compositions and comparing them with
60 analogous made with yellow corn flour and a control made with durum wheat semolina as a
61 reference. Physical characteristics and the behavior during cooking process were investigated,
62 the polyphenolic profile was analyzed, both on a qualitative, to better know its composition, and
63 quantitatively, to understand how the composition changes during the production and cooking
64 of pasta and whether it can be a good source of polyphenols for celiac people. Moreover, a
65 sensory analysis was carried out to characterize the perception and preferences towards this
66 new type of pasta in comparison with the other pasta already existing in the market.

67 **2. Material and Methods**

68 2.1. Reagents and raw materials

69 All chemical and standards in this study were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim,
70 Germany). Ultrapure water for physical analyses was obtained with a Millipore system (Milford,
71 MA, USA).: Purple corn flour was supplied by the “Millo corvo” Association (Morrazo,

72 Pontevedra, Spain), yellow corn flour, rice flour semolina and xanthan gum were purchased from
73 local supermarkets.

74 2.2. Formulation and sample features

75 A total of five samples were prepared, one reference and four gluten-free samples with two
76 different reformulations and two types of corn. The reference sample consisted of 100%
77 semolina flour (Sem). The other four, two with purple corn (P) and two with yellow corn (Y),
78 were formulated either with 100% corn flour (P100, Y100) or with 90% corn flour, 10% rice flour,
79 and 1.5% xanthan gum (P90, Y90).

80 2.2.1. Mixtures

81 Before preparing the mixtures, the moisture content of all flours was determined. Based on
82 these data, the amount of water required to achieve a final moisture content of 32-35%, optimal
83 for successful extrusion, was calculated (Merayo et al., 2011). Subsequently, two different
84 mixture methods were applied, as gluten-free samples require a pre-gelatinization process
85 (González et al., 2023). In every case a thermomixer (Thermomix TM31 VorWerk®, Wuppertal,
86 Germany) was used. The Sem sample was prepared at speed 7 and room temperature. For the
87 gluten-free samples, the method of Mestres et al. (1993) was used with some modifications:
88 20% of the corn flour or the corn-rice flour mixture were weighted and mixed with boiling water.
89 It was first blended for 3 minutes at 70°C, the remaining flour was added and mixed again for 9
90 minutes at 80°C. Once cooled, xanthan gum was added to the P90 and Y90 samples. All samples
91 were stored in airtight plastic bags in a refrigerator for 24 hours to allow proper hydration of the
92 flour granules. Part of these mixtures were stored for farther analyses.

93 2.2.2. Extrusion, Dehydration, and Storage

94 The selected pasta shape was spaghetti, made using an extruder (Brabender® KE 19/25,
95 Duisburg, Germany) with single screw and a 3mm diameter stainless steel die. To prevent gluten

96 from being denatured, the following parameters were used for the Sem pasta processing: T1
97 50°C, T2 55°C, T3 60°C, T4 65°C; feed speed 50 rpm; extruder speed 75 rpm. Conversely, higher
98 temperatures were preferred for the gluten-free samples to allow the starch to gelatinize and
99 retrograde, thereby improving the final pasta quality (Silva et al., 2016). For the gluten-free pasta
100 the conditions were T1 65°C, T2 70°C, T3 80°C, T4 85°C; feed speed and extruder speed were set
101 at 70 and 80 rpm, respectively. Duplicates for the process were done. Spaghetti of approximately
102 15 cm in length were cut, and samples reserved for subsequent analyses. The remaining pasta
103 was dehydrated using a dehydrator (Selecta[®]) at 50°C for 22 hours to reach 12% moisture
104 content, according to Italian pasta legislation (Decreto Del Presidente Della Repubblica n. 187
105 Del 9 Febbraio 2001, n.d.). Samples were collected at different stages; 3 times before cooking:
106 flour mixture (F), fresh extruded pasta (ND) and dried pasta (D); and twice after cooking as
107 described in section 2.3.2: cooked fresh pasta (NDC), and cooked dried pasta (DC).

108 2.3. Technological properties

109 2.3.1. Moisture Content

110 Moisture content was determined in triplicate for all samples following the AACC 44-15.02
111 (2009) method.

112 2.3.2. Cooking quality, *Cooking Time*, *Water Absorption*, *Cooking Loss*, and *Swelling Index*

113 The "optimal cooking time" (OCT) is defined as the time required for pasta to reach the desired
114 cooking, usually "al dente" (Figure 1). All the quality parameters related with OCT were
115 performed in triplicate according to the reference method (AACC 66-50.01 (2010)).

116 2.3.3. Color

117 The color of flour (F), dried (D) and cooked (DC) pasta was evaluated in triplicate using the CIE-
118 LAB tristimulus color system with a spectrophotometer (CM-2600d, Konica Minolta, Chiyoda,
119 Japan) under D65 illuminant and 10° standard observer. After calibration, the three CIELAB

120 coordinates L* (lightness), a* (green/red), and b* (yellow/blue) were assessed. Additionally, the
121 hue (h) and Chroma (C) values were calculated according to the following formulae: Hue (h) =
122 $\arctan b/a$; Chroma (C) = $\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$

123 2.3.4. Texture Analysis

124 Textural properties were determined in a TA-Xt.plus Texture Analyzer (Texture Technologies
125 Corp., USA) at approximately 22 °C. Firmness (N) was measured in D and ND pasta and repeated
126 seven times per lot. For its determination, one unit of pasta (5 cm. approximately) was aligned
127 to cut using a Blade Set (HDP/BSK, Warner-Bratzler) at 2.0 mm/s using 30 kg cell load. Texture
128 Profile Analysis (TPA) was carried out on DC pasta, eight times per lot. Samples were axially
129 compressed to 60% at 2 mm/s with a 5 kg load cell. Hardness (N), cohesiveness (no dimension),
130 springiness (no dimension) and chewiness (N) were calculated based on the force–time curve.

131 2.4. Chemical Properties

132 2.4.1. Polyphenol Extraction

133 Polyphenols were extracted from each sample at every production stage following the method
134 by Rodriguez et al. (2024) with some modifications. For F, ND, and D samples, the samples were
135 ground into a powder, and 50 mg were weighed, followed by the addition of 1 mL of a methanol-
136 water (50:50) solution containing 0.1% formic acid. For NDC and DC samples, 50 mg of pasta
137 were homogenized with 1 mL of the same solution using a homogenizer (Ultra-turrax T18 basic,
138 IKA®, Germany). All samples were vortexed for 1 minute at 7000 rpm, sonicated for 15 minutes
139 at room temperature, and then centrifuged at 4000 g at 4°C for 10 minutes. This extraction
140 process was repeated twice, using 0.5 mL of the solution to obtain a total of 2 ml of extract. All
141 extractions were performed in triplicate.

142 2.4.2. Individual Polyphenol analysis by HPLC-MS/MS

143 For the identification and quantification of individual polyphenols the methodology described
144 by Rodriguez et al. (2024) was used. Identification was carried out in the flours and then the
145 most abundant compounds in the samples were quantified. The HPLC with a quaternary pump
146 (G1311A) was coupled with a diode array detector (Agilent G1315B) and an Agilent 6530
147 Accurate-Mass Q-TOF LC/MS with electrospray ionization (ESI) with Jet Stream technology
148 (Agilent Technologies). The target compounds were separated on a Phenomenex Luna C18
149 column (5 μ m, 4.6 mm \times 150 mm), set at 25 $^{\circ}$ C. Data acquisition and processing were conducted
150 using Masshunter Data Acquisition B.05.01 and Masshunter Qualitative Analysis B.07.00 SP2
151 software (Agilent Technologies). Compounds were identified by comparing mass spectra and
152 retention times with the corresponding standards. When standards were unavailable,
153 identification was achieved by predicting the chemical formula from accurate ion mass
154 measurements and cross-referencing with data from relevant literature.

155 2.4.3. Total Polyphenol by Folin Ciocalteu

156 Total polyphenols were determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) method. In a 96-well plate, 10
157 μ l/well of extract, gallic acid standard, or blank was added, followed by 150 μ l/well of Folin-
158 Ciocalteu solution at 6%. The absorbance was then measured at 725 nm using a UV-Vis plate
159 reader (Powerwave XS, Biotek[®]). The results were expressed as milligrams of gallic acid
160 equivalents (GAE) per grams of dry weight. All analyses were performed in triplicate.

161 2.4.4. Antioxidant Capacity Assays: DPPH and FRAP

162 For both assays, a 96-well plate was used, with 10 μ l/well extract, Trolox solution or blank (EtOH).
163 For the DPPH assay, a 100 μ M DPPH reagent solution was prepared. After incubation in the dark
164 with continuous shaking for 1 hour, the absorbance was measured at 517 nm. For the FRAP
165 assay, the FRAP reagent solution was prepared by mixing acetate buffer (pH 3.6), TPTZ, and ferric
166 chloride in a 10:1:1 ratio. After incubation at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 15 minutes the absorbance at 593 nm was

167 recorded. The results were expressed as milligrams of Trolox equivalents (TAE) per gram of dry
168 weight. All the analysis were done in triplicate.

169 2.5. Sensory Analysis

170 Thirty-one naïve consumers (eighteen female) were recruited with the only condition that they
171 were frequent pasta consumers. The sensory test was carried out at CSIC-ICTAN's facilities in
172 individual sensory booths with standard lighting and temperature. Each pasta was cooked until
173 "al dente" and presented to the panelists within 1 min after cooking. All samples were presented
174 at the same time in reusable plastic bowls, with the same amount of pasta (5 g) and with 4 drops
175 of extra virgin olive oil. The panelists evaluated the samples in two different tasks. The first task
176 was a Flash Profile and the second a best-worst scaling. The semolina sample was presented
177 twice with a different code in order to check reliability. The panelists filled up the questionnaires
178 using individual tablets. Data were collected using Sensesbit software (Galicia, Spain).

179 2.5.1. Flash Profile

180 We followed the methodology proposed by Delarue et al. (2015). Briefly: assessors were first
181 gathered to get a joint short information session on how to perform the task and on how to use
182 the tablet. When everybody was confident and understood the task, they were brought to the
183 individual sensory booths. There they were presented with all the samples and they started the
184 test. The test consisted on generating their own free-choice vocabulary that better covered the
185 sensory variations in the six samples (five different ones plus the repeated sample). The panelists
186 could employ as much time as they needed and they could use as many attributes as they
187 wanted. For each attribute, they ranked the samples according to their intensity on an ordinal
188 scale anchored from 'lower' to 'higher'. The assessors were allowed to apply the same rank to
189 two or more samples if no difference was perceived.

190 2.5.2. Best-Worst Scaling

191 After performing the flash profiling, the assessors were asked to perform a short task of best-
192 worst scaling. According to their preference, and after having tasted all the samples in the
193 previous analysis, they had to choose which one was the best sample and which one the worst.
194 The selection was mandatory. This was an approximation to the test presented by Jaeger et al.
195 (2008).

196 2.5.3. Ethical Statement

197 Sensory analysis followed CSIC's ethic and data protection protocols. Participants in the sensory
198 analysis gave informed consent before participating in the analysis. They were informed that
199 they were able to withdraw at any time without giving a reason, they were provided with
200 allergens information and with the following information about personal data processing: “all
201 data captured will be confidential and anonymized and will be only used for research purposes”.
202 The tested products were safe for consumption.

203 2.6. Statistical Analysis

204 All data were processed using R (R Core Team, 2024) in R Studio (Posit team, 2024). Data were
205 checked for normality and homoscedasticity using Shapiro and Levene tests, respectively. One-
206 way ANOVA was performed using Bonferroni adjustment for post-hoc tests in physicochemical
207 data, the package rstatix was used (Kassambara, 2023). The same package was used to perform
208 two-way ANOVA with holm correction for evaluating the effect of the processing (drying,
209 cooking, etc) and sample on some of the parameters. Spearman correlation between
210 polyphenols and chemical parameters were also calculated. For flash profile the data were
211 organised in ranked data per panelist, analyzed individually using Principal Component Analysis
212 (PCA), a sensory map was created using multi-block Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) and a
213 Hierarchical Cluster on the MFA (HCPC) with the FactoMineR package (Lê et al., 2008). The
214 package factoextra was used for visualization (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020) Reliability was

215 checked via Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The best-worst scaling data was analysed using bwsTools
216 package (White, 2020).

217 2.7. Data availability

218 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at
219 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13284279>

220

221 **3. Results and discussion**

222 3.1. Technological properties

223 3.1.1. Moisture Content and Cooking Quality

224 Moisture values were around 12 and 13 % (Table 1). These values were similar to those observed
225 in commercial spaghetti and in gluten-free pasta with corn and/or rice flour (Bolarinwa & Oyesiji,
226 2021). The moisture of samples with 100 % of corn flour (Y100 and P100) showed no significant
227 differences with the wheat sample (Sem), showing the lowest moisture values. The presence of
228 xanthan gum in Y90 and P90 samples, due to its ability to absorb water, could be related to the
229 highest moisture values observed in the pasta (Kraithong et al., 2023).

230 Cooking quality with respect to the OCT was measured by water absorption, cooking loss and
231 swelling index (Table 1) and was affected by the type of corn flour (yellow or purple) and the
232 presence of rice flour and xanthan gum. A high cooking quality can be defined as the result of
233 high water absorption and low cooking losses. Regarding water absorption, it was observed
234 higher values ($p<0.05$) in samples made with purple corn than in those with the yellow one.
235 Cooking loss for all the pasta samples was much lower than 12%, a value considered by the AACC
236 (Delcour, 2010) to be the limit for quality pasta. Comparing free-gluten pasta, samples with
237 purple corn (P100 and P90) showed the lowest ($p<0.05$) values indicating better technological
238 quality. Higher cooking loss were observed in rich polyphenol dry spaghetti made with semolina

239 and xanthan gum (Freire et al., 2024). Pasta made with xanthan gum (Y90 and P90) showed
240 higher water absorption and lower cooking loss than their xanthan-free counterparts (Y100 and
241 P100, Table 1). The presence of xanthan gum improves the cooking quality regardless the use of
242 purple or yellow corn, due to its gelling capacity allows to form a network that reinforces the
243 structure (Scarton & Clerici, 2022). In relation to the swelling Index, it was observed that the
244 semolina sample had the highest values; however, no clear trend was found in the rest of the
245 samples.

246 3.1.2. Color analysis

247 Color is the first factor that influences a consumer's attention to purchase a food product. In the
248 case of pasta, its color largely depends on the appearance of flour used in its production, as this
249 is its main ingredient, as can be observed in Fig. 1 Therefore, the color differences observed
250 among the flours used to make the spaghetti were reflected in the final products, both dried
251 and cooked pasta (Table 2).

252 The samples made with wheat semolina showed the highest ($p < 0.05$) lightness values and the
253 lowest ($p < 0.05$) redness values, for flour, dried and cooked pasta (Table 2). Between the gluten-
254 free samples, lower lightness and redness values were observed for the P100 and P90 dried and
255 cooked pasta. The b^* parameter is an indicator of colors ranging from blue (negative) to yellow
256 (positive). All the samples scored positive values, although samples with purple-corn had the
257 lowest values ($p < 0.05$) and very close to zero. Yellow-corn pasta (dried and cooked) had
258 significantly higher b^* value than Sem pasta. Hue is a parameter closely related with what we
259 understand as traditional colors (greenish, reddish, etc) where 0 and 360 correspond to red, 90
260 to yellow, 180 to green and 270 to blue hues (Pathare et al., 2013). We can clearly see that this
261 parameter was the one that better differentiate the samples with purple corn from the rest
262 (Table 2) as P100 and P90 scored significantly lower values (closer to red hue) than the rest
263 (towards yellow hue).

264 Additionally, chroma was also calculated allowing for an analysis that is closer to what the
265 consumer is able to perceive visually as color intensity (Pathare et al., 2013). Samples P100 and
266 P90 (dried and cooked) showed the lowest ($p<0.05$) chroma values, so consumers perceive a
267 lower intensity of their color. Although statistically significant, the addition of rice flour and
268 xanthan gum did not affected much the absolute numbers of color parameters. Oliver et al.
269 (1992) proposed a Flour Color Index (FCI) to measure the whiteness of the flour subtracting the
270 a^* and b^* to the L^* value when red or purple pigments are present. FCI was calculated for flour
271 samples and it showed statistical differences between all the flours. The lowest value was for
272 wheat semolina flour (48.4 ± 0.3) and the highest the Y100 flour (65.2 ± 0.1) and Y90 flour
273 (62.0 ± 0.2). The flour from purple corn showed an FCI of 52.7 ± 0.4 for P100 and 55.4 ± 0.2 for P90.
274 This means that “whitest” flour was the semolina one and the least white the corn flour.

275 Moreover, these samples suffered important variations during processing. Drying affected all
276 the samples, significantly decreasing ($p<0.05$) L^* and hue values (Table 2). Drying of Y100 an Y90
277 samples significantly increased both a^* and b^* and therefore, chroma too. For Sem, P100 and
278 P90 samples these values were significantly decreased. Cooking of the dried pasta also affected
279 color parameters: L^* and hue values were significantly increased ($p<0.05$) and a^* and chroma
280 values significantly decreased for all samples.

281

282 3.1.3. Texture

283 The texture of pasta is closely related to consumer acceptability. In that sense, we analyzed the
284 firmness of dry and cooked pasta. Moreover, a TPA was conducted (Table 1) with cooked pasta
285 as this test mimics the mastication process.

286 The lowest firmness of dry pasta corresponded to semolina ones (35.90 N). Gluten-free pasta
287 showed firmness values between 63.86 (P90) and 132.45 N (Y100), but no clear differences were
288 observed between them. Once cooked, as expected, the firmness of the pasta decreased

289 significantly. Sample Y90 showed the highest ($p < 0.05$) firmness values (4.22 N), and no
290 differences were observed among the other samples (Table 1).

291 The TPA indicated that sample Sem was the one with lowest hardness value but only significantly
292 lower compared with Y90, mainly due to the high variability in the gluten-free samples (Table 1).

293 Cohesiveness is a good indicator of how the sample is kept compact through cooking. Pasta
294 made with semolina showed significantly higher values than the rest, closely related with water
295 absorption values (Table 1). Sample Y90 had significantly the lowest springiness value, with no
296 significant differences among the others. The combination of rice flour and xanthan gum with
297 the yellow-corn flour had made to the sample to lose part of its ability to spring back after
298 deformation. High springiness and firmness values are typical of rice flour pasta (Marti et al.,
299 2010) but pasta diameter is also a critical factor in increasing springiness (Marti & Pagani, 2013).
300 Chewiness was similar for all samples with no statistically significant differences.

301 We can conclude that pasta made from purple corn presented a good technological and cooking
302 quality.

303 3.2. Chemical properties

304 3.2.1. Identification of Polyphenols

305 By means of HPLC-DAD-QToF in the ESI probe and in both positive and negative modes, 59
306 compounds have been identified, including anthocyanins, flavonols, phenylpolyamines, and
307 other potential bioactive compounds, as reported in Table 3. In purple corn, 44 compounds have
308 been detected, while in yellow corn and semolina only 17 and 14 compounds have been found
309 respectively.

310 Going into more detail, the main group of compounds identified in purple corn were
311 anthocyanins, which were both in their $m+z$ mode and in the UV-Vis Chromatogram at 520 nm.

312 As reported previously by Rodriguez et al. (2024) and Peniche-Pavía & Tiessen (2020), derivatives

313 of cyanidin, pelargonidin, and peonidin have been identified by specific fragments with m/z at
314 287.05, 271.07, and 301.07, respectively. These compounds have been identified in conjugated
315 forms with sugars, malonyl, or other substitution of the main structure, making them more
316 resistant to environmental stress including temperature. This was the case of cyanidin 3-
317 glucoside (m/z 449.1227), pelargonidin 3-glucoside (m/z 433.1257), cyanidin 3-
318 malonylglucoside (m/z 535.1091), and cyanidin 3-(6-*p*-caffeoyl) glucoside (m/z 611.1419).

319 Additionally, unknown compounds with fragments at 287.05, for which no confirmation was
320 found in the literature, were identified, at the same ionization mode and wavelength of
321 absorbance, as anthocyanins (Fig. S2). For this reason, they were classified as cyanidin
322 derivatives. Among these are molecules with masses at 800.2054, 638.1307, 622.1508, and
323 655.1688, which require further study for their identification.

324 Regarding flavonols, all were identified in the negative mode and at a wavelength of 360 nm. In
325 agreement with Das & Singh (2016) and Rodriguez et al. (2024), quercetin (m/z 301.0465) and
326 its derivatives were identified, all containing the parent fragment and conjugated either with
327 sugars or other groups. Among these, those present in the highest quantities are quercetin-3-
328 glucoside (m/z 463.1018), quercetin-3-rutinoside (m/z 609.1613), and quercetin 3-(6''-
329 malonyl-glucoside) (m/z 549.1455) (Table S1). At this same wavelength, caffeic acid (m/z
330 179.0407) was also detected in yellow corn.

331 Regarding compounds identified at a wavelength of 280 nm, tryptophan (m/z 205.0963) was
332 found in all samples, being most abundant in semolina, along with *p*-coumaric acid (m/z
333 163.0452) and ferulic acid (m/z 193), which were present in higher amounts in purple corn (Fig.
334 S1). Following the work of Dinelli et al. (2009), compounds derived from apigenin were identified
335 in semolina under negative ionization, including apigenin-6/8-C-pentoside-8/6-C-hexoside (m -
336 z 593.1709), vanillin (m/z 151.0458), and a flavone, glycosylated and acetylated 3',4',5'-
337 trihydroxy-3,7-dimethylflavone (m/z 533.1479).

338 Concerning flavanones, both in purple and yellow corn, 5,3'-dihydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxy-6,8-
339 dimethylallyl-flavanone (or prenylultiline) was detected, with a mass of 454.2352 (Oliveira et al.,
340 2012). Furthermore, in corn samples, phenylpolyamines derived from coumaric acid were
341 abundantly found, all of them in the positive ionization. There are not many studies regarding
342 their presence in corn, but thanks to Bento-Silva et al. (2020), various compounds were
343 identified, including N-coumaroyl spermidine (m/z 292.2035), N,N'-dicoumaroyl spermidine
344 (m/z 438.2402), and N,N'-dicoumaroyl putrescine (m/z 381.1757). These compounds can be
345 conjugated with feruloyl groups, leading to compounds such as N,N'-coumaroyl feruloyl
346 putrescine (m/z 468.2526), N,N'-diferuloyl putrescine (441.2044), and N,N'-coumaroyl feruloyl
347 putrescine (m/z 411.1939). Generally, compounds containing spermidine show a main
348 fragments at m/z 204.10 and 292.19, while those containing putrescine at 265.16 and 177.77.

349 Additionally, in corn samples, an unknown compound was identified, which is one of the most
350 significant findings despite no bibliographic correspondence being found. This compound has a
351 positive mass of 493.2775 and its corresponding fragment at m/z 265.09, which is the same as
352 those found in molecules containing putrescine. For this reason, it was identified as a putrescine
353 derivative, but as the other unknown molecules detected but not identified, further studies and
354 investigations are necessary.

355 This last peak at 493.2775 m/z co-elutes, with compound 800,2054 m/z . For quantification
356 purposes and because 493.2775 m/z does not show absorbance at 530nm, 800,2054 m/z
357 was selected and identified as a cyanidine derivative. In addition, two other peaks similar to the
358 latest have been found at RT 17.7 min: peonidin-3-(6''malonylglucoside) and cyanidin-3-
359 (dimalonylglucoside). Additionally, at RT 18.2 min there is the N-coumaroyl spermidine and the
360 N,N'-dicoumaroyl spermidine. For both cases it was chosen to quantify the peak with the largest
361 area, so in the first case the cyanidin and in the second the dicoumaroyl (Fig. S1).

362 3.2.2. Quantification of anthocyanins in purple corn samples

363 Since the purpose of this work is to study the potential of purple corn flour as an alternative
364 ingredient for producing a healthier gluten-free pasta, Table 4 reports the concentration,
365 calculated in $\mu\text{g/g}$ on a dry weight basis, of the main quantifiable compounds. The calibration
366 curve of the same compound was used for all compounds, except for cyanidin, quercetin, and
367 polyamine derivatives, for which the concentration was calculated using cyanidin 3-glucoside,
368 quercetin 3-glucoside, and p-coumaric standards, respectively. In the flour mixtures, regardless
369 of the formulation, the compounds present in the highest quantities were tryptophan (up to 191
370 $\mu\text{g/g}$), phenylpolyamines, particularly N,N'-dicoumaroyl-spermidine, ferulic acid, and p-
371 coumaric acid, with the latter two ranging from 12.16 to 21.98 $\mu\text{g/g}$. For anthocyanins, their
372 presence is highest in the P100 sample, with cyanidin 3-malonylglucoside being the most
373 abundant at 18.26 $\mu\text{g/g}$, followed by cyanidin 3-glucoside and cyanidin 3-(3'', 6''-
374 dimalonylglucoside) at 14.34 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 4.87 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively. For flavonols, their presence is
375 generally higher in the P90 sample, with quercetin 3-diglucoside being the most abundant at
376 2.89 $\mu\text{g/g}$.

377 A closer analysis reveals that, in both samples, the cooking process statistically significantly
378 influences the loss of polyphenols (Table S1). Anthocyanins are among the most affected: for
379 instance, cyanidin 3-glucoside in dried pasta decreases by 81.75% in P100 and 67.67% in P90
380 after cooking. Similarly, pelargonidin 3-(6'' malonylglucoside) shows a reduction of 78.31% and
381 59.99% in P100 and P90, respectively, in the ND sample, fresh pasta. Notably, except for some
382 few compounds, the reduction is always greater in dried pasta than in fresh pasta. This excessive
383 reduction during cooking, however, is not as pronounced for phenylpolyamines, ferulic acid, and
384 coumaric acid, especially in the P90 sample, where the reduction never exceeds 70%. Unlike
385 anthocyanins, these compounds are more significantly lost during cooking in fresh pasta than in
386 dried pasta. Quercetin derivatives are also affected by cooking but in a more heterogeneous
387 manner. However, regarding both extrusion and dehydration processes, some compounds
388 increase in concentration. Indeed, during extrusion, statistically significant increases are

389 observed in tryptophan, p-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, and phenylpolyamines. For example, the
390 polyamine N,N'-coumaroyl feruloyl putrescine increases by 56.97% in the P100 sample and
391 75.22% in the P90 sample from the mixture to the pasta. Except for ferulic acid, the reformulated
392 pasta (90) tends to increase the concentration of these compounds during extrusion. The
393 anthocyanin family behaves differently, as, despite some variability between the two samples,
394 there is no significant difference in concentrations before and after the extrusion process.
395 However, it is noteworthy that pasta made solely with corn flour shows lesser degradation in
396 anthocyanins than pasta with added rice flour. The dehydration process, a crucial production
397 step, differentially influences compounds in various samples. Among anthocyanins, only the
398 unknown compound 800.2054 [M-H]⁺ shows a statistical reduction in both samples, while
399 cyanidin 3-(dimalonylglucoside) decreases only in the P90 sample, from 3.83 to 2.14 µg/g. Most
400 phenylpolyamines undergo a significant reduction, whereas among quercetin derivatives, only
401 quercetin-3-O-(6''-O-malonyl)-glucoside statistically reduces by 42.87% and 25.33% in the P100
402 and P90 samples, respectively.

403 Finally, another small detail can be noted. In cooked pasta (NDC and DC), the concentrations are
404 almost always higher in absolute value in the P90 samples compared to the P100 samples,
405 despite having 10% white rice flour, which is poorer in polyphenols than purple corn flour, as
406 confirmed by the initial concentrations in the flour mixtures. Although no significant differences
407 were statistically observed between the two samples, some observations are warranted. This
408 could be explained by the gelling property of xanthan gum, which, as explained by García-Ochoa
409 et al. (2000), can aggregate through intermolecular forces and create a network more resistant
410 to external stress. This potentially could trap polyphenolic compounds within the pasta matrix.
411 This theory can be further confirmed by the results obtained from physical-technological tests:
412 it was noted that the addition of xanthan results in higher water absorption and lower cooking
413 loss. Since polyphenols are water-soluble and most are logically lost in water during cooking,
414 this explains why pasta with the addition of the hydrocolloid, although poorer in polyphenols

415 due to the addition of rice flour, ends up having a higher concentration of some of these
416 polyphenols. This can also be confirmed by noting that, with a few exceptions, the reduction of
417 polyphenols is often greater in the P100 sample than in the P90 sample.

418 Summarizing the above, in the anthocyanin group, the most abundant compounds are cyanidin
419 derivatives, especially cyanidin 3-malonylglucoside and cyanidin 3-glucoside, in agreement with
420 previous research (Blanch et al., 2023). However, anthocyanins, being thermolabile and water-
421 soluble, are among those most degraded during pasta cooking, as also reported by Camelo-
422 Méndez et al. (2018). On the other hand, a new category of compounds, phenylpolyamines,
423 requires further study. These compounds are part of the pathway for the biosynthesis of colored
424 pigments in corn (Peniche-Pavía & Tiessen, 2020) and appear to be more thermoresistant
425 compared to the other compounds studied, including quercetin derivatives, which are more
426 thermolabile and present in lower quantities. Additionally, some of the phenylamines here
427 described could liberate the phenyl group during digestion and absorption acting as reservoirs
428 of phenolic compounds in the gastrointestinal system.

429 3.2.3. Folin, FRAP, DPPH

430 These assays provide an overview of the antioxidant properties, expressed as $\mu\text{g TE/g}$, and the
431 presence of polyphenols, expressed as $\mu\text{g GAE/g}$, and how they change during the production
432 process, as reported in Table 5. In general, the samples with the highest values in all assays are
433 those based on purple corn. The Folin-Ciocalteu assay shows initial values of 1.54 and 1.35 μg
434 GAE/g , reducing to 0.30 and 0.41 $\mu\text{g GAE/g}$ for P100 and P90, respectively. For antioxidant assays,
435 the values of the flour mixtures range from 4063.48 to 5676.70 $\mu\text{g TE/g}$, decreasing to 1713.97
436 $\mu\text{g TE/g}$ in the case of DC pasta in the reformulated sample. Regarding yellow corn pasta, higher
437 FRAP and DPPH values can be observed compared to semolina, which is the poorest in terms of
438 polyphenolic compounds. All corn flour-based samples, both purple and yellow, positively
439 influence the extrusion process, leading to an increase in values in all assays. This is not always

440 the case for semolina. Conversely, consistent with the quantification, dehydration and cooking
441 are the steps that most significantly reduce these values, as also confirmed by the article by
442 Blanch et al. (2023). Finally, as noted in the quantification, the 100% purple corn flour mixture
443 shows higher values in all assays compared to the reformulated counterpart. However, in
444 cooked pasta, the opposite occurs, with P90 samples having statistically higher values for the
445 Folin and FRAP assays (Table 5). In absolute terms, the same trend is observed for yellow corn
446 flour samples, although not statistically significant. This supports the theory of the potential role
447 of xanthan gum in reducing the loss of polyphenolic compounds during cooking, as discussed in
448 the previous paragraph

449 3.2.4. Correlations

450 Correlations are useful to further substantiate the obtained results. For purple corn, the
451 concentration of total polyphenols, anthocyanins, and phenylpolyamines was compared with
452 different assays. For yellow corn and semolina samples, the Folin assay was also compared with
453 the FRAP assay. All correlations were significant and exceeded the value of 0.5 (Table S2). When
454 comparing anthocyanins and a^* and color parameters we observed that the correlations were
455 the lowest of all, positive for a^* ($r=0.69$) and negative for hue ($r=-0.52$). The highest correlation
456 values were found between total polyphenols and FRAP ($r=0.97$) and total anthocyanins and
457 FRAP ($r=0.95$). The DPPH assay had lower correlation values with $r=0.77$ and 0.70 with
458 polyphenols and anthocyanins, respectively. When comparing the Folin and FRAP assays for
459 each cereal type, the lowest correlation is observed in semolina, with an $r=0.71$, followed by
460 yellow corn with $r=0.85$, and purple corn with $r=0.92$.

461 3.3. Sensory Analysis

462 Seventeen out of the thirty-one panelists were between 18 and 35 years old. With regards to
463 pasta consumption five of them reported to consume it more than once per week and 21 at

464 least once per week. Thus, we can say this was a panel of high frequent pasta consumers and
465 balanced in gender and age.

466 3.3.1. Flash profile

467 A total of 211 attributes were elicited by the panelists. The median number of attributes from
468 each panelist was six, being fourteen the maximum and three the minimum. From these, 75
469 were appearance related attributes (including color), 18 odor/smell related, 72 texture related,
470 and 46 flavor/taste related. The most repeated attribute was hardness, 81% of the panelists
471 used it. Yellowness and brightness were used by 39% and 35% of the panelists, respectively. The
472 most used attribute related to flavor was bitterness that was used by 32% of the analysts. It is
473 noteworthy that although the samples P100 and P90 were of purple color, only seven panelists
474 used it as an attribute, being yellow or darkness more preferable attributes to highlight the color
475 difference.

476 The panelists' descriptive efficiency was evaluated by analyzing individual PCA. By comparing
477 the explained variance throughout the principal components vs the number of attributes used.
478 In general, most of the panelists had a relatively high efficiency in differentiating the samples as
479 the variance was spread along the number of principal components. Only panelists 8 and 9 had
480 a "low efficiency", as variance was almost totally explained by the first two principal components
481 having elicited 12 and 9 attributes, respectively (Fig. S3). As a measure of reliability, we included
482 a repeated sample. Analyzing the paired results for the two equal samples we obtained that
483 there were not significant differences between them (V wilcoxon= 1556, $p=0.782$, effect
484 size=0.035). This is in agreement with the proximity of both samples in the MFA plot (Fig. 2).
485 Flash profile with naïve consumers is not the typical approach (Delarue et al., 2015), however
486 our results are in agreement with existing literature (Heo et al., 2023)

487 The MFA showed that with the first two principal components an 82.09% of the variance was
488 explained (45.53% for the first and 36.57% for the second), being fully explained with five

489 components. Using these two dimensions, we can see three clear clustered groups: one for the
490 wheat samples (S1, S2), one for the yellow corn samples (Y100, Y90) and another for the purple
491 corn samples (P100, P90) (Fig. 2). Sem samples and Y samples have similar loading on the first
492 component, whereas P samples had an opposite loading for first dimension and different for
493 second dimension. When grouped by flour type, the confidence lines show significant
494 differences between the clusters ($p < 0.05$) but not differences ($p > 0.05$) between the samples
495 within these groups. This clustering can be also observed after performing a HCPC; with the
496 clusters of wheat and yellow corn samples closer to each other than to the purple corn samples
497 (Fig. S4). We can say that there was more sensory differences between purple-corn pasta and
498 the rest than between wheat and yellow-corn pasta. In this case, flour type affected the sensory
499 perception more than being gluten-free.

500 The MFA's correlation plot (Fig.3) and the results from the HCPC both show which of the
501 attributes contribute more to each principal component and clusters, respectively. Dimension 1
502 is driven on the positive side by attributes regarding dark colors, "sandy" texture and bitter
503 flavor and on the negative with homogeneity of color and appearance and traditional pasta
504 flavor. This is in agreement with the cluster of P100 and P90 samples positioning positively on
505 this side. That is, samples with purple corn were evaluated as darker, with grainy texture and
506 more bitter. On the other hand, attributes contributing to dimension 2 are those related with
507 hardness and color intensity on the positive side and smell on the negative side. Wheat samples
508 are located towards the negative side of dimension 2, meaning that "pasta smell" was a clear
509 attribute for this samples. Yellow corn samples are located on the positive side, showing that
510 color intensity (yellow color) and hardness were the main sensory attributes differentiating
511 them from wheat pasta samples. The different perception in texture between Y and Sem
512 samples is in agreement with the hardness on the textural analysis.

513 On the MFA, Y90 is the one higher on dimension 2 where hardness has more importance (Fig.2,3)
514 and this sample was the one significantly higher hardness than Sem (Table 1). The inclusion of
515 rice flour and xanthan gum in the Y90 and P90 formulations had similar effect increasing
516 hardness perception of the pasta as they increase in the second dimension plot (Fig. 2,3).

517 The flash profile analysis showed us which sensorial characteristics of the samples were more
518 important for the consumers in order to differentiate them. Naïve consumers clearly perceived
519 the samples as in three groups, coinciding with the flour type. Even though this test does not
520 analyze consumer likeness, some negative attributes were elicited for the gluten-free purple
521 corn pasta (bitterness, sandy texture). Having identified these issues, future pasta formulations
522 with purple corn flour should focus on countering the bitter flavor and the grainy texture. In the
523 case of gluten-free yellow corn pasta, texture, color and smell were an indicative of differences
524 when compared to the wheat semolina ones. Future action should focus on these attributes.

525 3.4.2. Best-Worst Preference Test

526 We can see on Table 6 that the Sem sample was selected more times as the best sample and
527 that P100 sample was selected more times as the worst one. This gives as an idea of the
528 consumer preference for the wheat pasta samples over the gluten-free versions. Using the best-
529 worst difference we can establish the following preference for the samples
530 $S > Y100 > Y90 > P90 > P100$. This is in agreement with the results from the logit modelling where
531 both the utility coefficients and the hit rate show same preference (Table 6). There is a linear
532 relationship between the logit modelling coefficients and the best-worst data (Utility Coeff =
533 $2.312 * BW + 0.051$, $R^2 = 0.998$). Jaeger and Cardello (2009) also found a strong linear relationships
534 between both measurements. Hit rates above 0.5 yield positive mean utility coefficients
535 whereas below that middle point yield negative coefficients. If we check the confidence intervals
536 we see that Sem sample CI is the only one not overlapping with any of the rest. However, we
537 should analyze this with care as no replications were used for any of the other samples. The

538 choice probability makes it easier to interpret, as the sum of all probabilities is 100%. The
539 likelihood of Sem sample being chosen in preference to P100 sample is approximately 10:1.
540 There seem to be no preference between P100 and P90 samples but Y100 is around 1.7 times
541 more likely to be chosen than Y90. This preference test shows us that purple corn pasta would
542 need better refinement in order to compete in the market with yellow corn or wheat pasta.

543 4. Conclusion

544 Pasta made from purple corn presented a good technological and cooking quality. Sensorial
545 analysis showed that future formulations of this kind of pasta would need further research in
546 order to countermeasure the perceived bitterness and grainy texture. Purple corn pasta
547 presents itself as an excellent alternative gluten free pasta, rich in polyphenols, mainly
548 anthocyanins, some of which have shown to resist partially the cooking process making them
549 accessible for their digestion.

550

551 **Author contributions**

552 **Gonzalo Delgado-Pando:** Methodology, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing –
553 original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Marco Acerbo:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing –
554 original draft. **Tatiana Pintado:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing –
555 review & editing. **Sonia de Pascual-Teresa:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources,
556 Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

557 **Declaration of competing interest**

558 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
559 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

560 **Funding:** This work was supported by the Spanish MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ (Grant
561 number PID2019-107009RB-100) and European Union's Erasmus + Programme (M.A.)

562 **Acknowledgements**

563 Authors would like to thank Graciela Blanch, Nel Freire and Asociación Millo corvo for supplying
564 the purple corn (Morrazo, Pontevedra, Spain) and David Gutiérrez and Angel Valbuena for the
565 assistance with the extruder work.

566 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

567 **Data statement**

568 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in

569 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13284279>

570 **References**

571 AACC International. (2009). Method 44-15.02. In *Approved Methods of Analysis 11th edition*.

572 AACC International. (2010). Method 66-50.01. In *Approved Methods of Analysis 11th edition*.

573 Bento-Silva, A., Duarte, N., Mecha, E., Belo, M., Vaz Patto, M. C., & Bronze, M. do R. (2020).

574 Hydroxycinnamic Acids and Their Derivatives in Broa, a Traditional Ethnic Maize Bread.

575 *Foods*, 9(10), Article 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9101471>

576 Blanch, G. P., de Pascual-Teresa, S., & Ruiz del Castillo, M. L. (2023). Study on the phenolic

577 composition and antioxidant properties of white-, yellow-, and black-corn (*Zea mays*

578 L.) foodstuffs. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 103(13), 6263–6271.

579 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.12697>

580 Bolarinwa, I. F., & Oyesiji, O. O. (2021). Gluten free rice-soy pasta: Proximate composition,

581 textural properties and sensory attributes. *Heliyon*, 7(1), e06052.

582 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06052>

583 Calabriso, N., Scoditti, E., Massaro, M., Maffia, M., Chieppa, M., Laddomada, B., & Carluccio,

584 M. A. (2022). Non-celiac gluten sensitivity and protective role of dietary polyphenols.

585 *Nutrients*, 14(13), 2679.

586 Camelo-Méndez, G. A., Tovar, J., & Bello-Pérez, L. A. (2018). Influence of blue maize flour on
587 gluten-free pasta quality and antioxidant retention characteristics. *Journal of Food*
588 *Science and Technology*, 55(7), 2739–2748. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-018-3196-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-018-3196-9)
589 9

590 Culetu, A., Duta, D. E., Papageorgiou, M., & Varzakas, T. (2021). The role of hydrocolloids in
591 gluten-free bread and pasta; rheology, characteristics, staling and glycemic index.
592 *Foods*, 10(12), 3121.

593 Das, A. K., & Singh, V. (2016). Antioxidative free and bound phenolic constituents in botanical
594 fractions of Indian specialty maize (*Zea mays* L.) genotypes. *Food Chemistry*, 201, 298–
595 306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.01.099>

596 Decreto Del Presidente Della Repubblica n. 187 Del 9 Febbraio 2001, Serie Generale n. 117 del
597 22 maggio 2001, Regolamento per la revisione della normativa sulla produzione e la
598 commercializzazione di sfarinati e paste alimentari. Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica
599 Italiana.

600 Del Rio, D., Rodriguez-Mateos, A., Spencer, J. P. E., Tognolini, M., Borges, G., & Crozier, A.
601 (2013). Dietary (poly)phenolics in human health: Structures, bioavailability, and
602 evidence of protective effects against chronic diseases. *Antioxidants and Redox*
603 *Signaling*, 18(ue 14), 1818–1892. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2012.4581>

604 Delarue, J., Lawlor, J. B., & Rogeaux, M. (Eds.). (2015). Woodhead Publishing Series in Food
605 Science, Technology and Nutrition. In *Rapid Sensory Profiling Techniques* (pp. xv–
606 xxviii). Woodhead Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-78242-248-8.50028-9>

607 Dinelli, G., Segura Carretero, A., Di Silvestro, R., Marotti, I., Fu, S., Benedettelli, S., Ghiselli, L., &
608 Fernández Gutiérrez, A. (2009). Determination of phenolic compounds in modern and
609 old varieties of durum wheat using liquid chromatography coupled with time-of-flight
610 mass spectrometry. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1216(43), 7229–7240.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2009.08.041>

612 Freire, C. D., Pinto, F. R., Almeida, D., & Gil, M. M. (2024). Linseed and xanthan gum in algae
613 pasta: Textural, sensory and antioxidant characteristics. *International Journal of Food*
614 *Science & Technology*, 59(8), 5477–5489. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijfs.17265>

615 Gao, Y., Janes, M. E., Chaiya, B., Brennan, M. A., Brennan, C. S., Prinyawiwatkul, W., S., A.,
616 Zannini, E., & Arendt, E. K. (2018). Gluten-free bakery and pasta products: Prevalence
617 and quality improvement. *International Journal of Food Science & Technology*, 53(1),
618 19-32 ,.

619 García-Ochoa, F., Santos, V. E., Casas, J. A., & Gómez, E. (2000). Xanthan gum: Production,
620 recovery, and properties. *Biotechnology Advances*, 18(7), 549–579.
621 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0734-9750\(00\)00050-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0734-9750(00)00050-1)

622 Giacco, R., Vitale, M., & Riccardi, G. (2016). Pasta: Role in diet. In B. Caballero, P. Finglas, & F.
623 Toldrá (Eds.), *The Encyclopedia of Food and Health* (pp. 242–245). Amsterdam.

624 Giménez, M. A., Drago, S. R., Greef, D., Gonzalez, R. J., Lobo, M. O., & Samman, N. C. (2012).
625 Rheological, functional and nutritional properties of wheat/broad bean (*Vicia faba*)
626 flour blends for pasta formulation. *Food Chemistry*, 134(1), 200–206.

627 González, L. C., Loubes, M. A., & Tolaba, M. P. (2023). Gluten Free Pasta Production and
628 Formulation Design. In M. F. de Escalada Pla & C. E. Genevois (Eds.), *Designing Gluten*
629 *Free Bakery and Pasta Products* (pp. 271–306). Springer International Publishing.
630 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-28344-4_8

631 Heo, J., Lee, S. J., Oh, J., Kim, M.-R., & Kwak, H. S. (2023). Comparison of descriptive analysis
632 and flash profile by naïve consumers and experts on commercial milk and yogurt
633 products. *Food Quality and Preference*, 110, 104946.
634 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2023.104946>

635 Husby, S., Koletzko, S., Korponay-Szabó, I. R., Mearin, M. L., Phillips, A., Shamir, R., ESPGHAN
636 Working Group on Coeliac Disease Diagnosis, ESPGHAN Gastroenterology Committee,
637 & European Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition. (2012).

638 European Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition guidelines
639 for the diagnosis of coeliac disease. *Journal of Pediatric Gastroenterology and*
640 *Nutrition*, 54(1), 136–160.

641 Jaeger, S. R., & Cardello, A. V. (2009). Direct and indirect hedonic scaling methods: A
642 comparison of the labeled affective magnitude (LAM) scale and best–worst scaling.
643 *Food Quality and Preference*, 20(3), 249–258.
644 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2008.10.005>

645 Jaeger, S. R., Jørgensen, A. S., Aaslyng, M. D., & Bredie, W. L. P. (2008). Best–worst scaling: An
646 introduction and initial comparison with monadic rating for preference elicitation with
647 food products. *Food Quality and Preference*, 19(6), 579–588.
648 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2008.03.002>

649 Kassambara, A. (2023). *rstatix: Pipe-Friendly Framework for Basic Statistical Tests* [R package
650 version 0.7.2]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rstatix>

651 Kassambara, A., & Mundt, F. (2020). *factoextra: Extract and Visualize the Results of*
652 *Multivariate Data Analyses* [R package version 1.0.7]. [https://CRAN.R-](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=factoextra)
653 [project.org/package=factoextra](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=factoextra)

654 King, J. A., Jeong, J., Underwood, F. E., Quan, J., Panaccione, N., Windsor, J. W., Coward, S.,
655 deBruyn, J., Ronksley, P. E., Shaheen, A.-A., Quan, H., Godley, J., Veldhuyzen Van
656 Zanten, S., Lebwohl, B., Ng, S. C., Ludvigsson, J. F., & Kaplan, G. G. (2020). Incidence of
657 Celiac Disease Is Increasing Over Time: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis.
658 *American Journal of Gastroenterology*, 115(4), 507–525.
659 <https://doi.org/10.14309/ajg.0000000000000523>

660 Kraithong, S., Theppawong, A., Lee, S., & Huang, R. (2023). Understanding of hydrocolloid
661 functions for enhancing the physicochemical features of rice flour and noodles. *Food*
662 *Hydrocolloids*, 142, 108821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2023.108821>

663 Lê, S., Josse, J., & Husson, F. (2008). FactoMineR: An R Package for Multivariate Analysis.
664 *Journal of Statistical Software*, 25, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v025.i01>

665 Marti, A., & Pagani, M. A. (2013). What can play the role of gluten in gluten free pasta? *Trends*
666 *in Food Science & Technology*, 31(1), 63–71.

667 Marti, A., Seetharaman, K., & Pagani, M. A. (2010). Rice-based pasta: A comparison between
668 conventional pasta-making and extrusion-cooking. *Journal of Cereal Science*, 52(3),
669 404–409.

670 Merayo, Y. A., González, R. J., Drago, S. R., Torres, R. L., & De Greef, D. M. (2011). Extrusion
671 conditions and zea mays endosperm hardness affecting gluten-free spaghetti quality.
672 *International Journal of Food Science & Technology*, 46(11), 2321–2328.
673 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.2011.02752.x>

674 Mestres, C., Colonna, P., Alexandre, M. C., & Matencio, F. (1993). Comparison of Various
675 Processes for Making Maize Pasta. *Journal of Cereal Science*, 17(3), 277–290.
676 <https://doi.org/10.1006/jcrs.1993.1026>

677 Murray, J. C., Kiszonas, A. M., & Morris, C. F. (2017). Pasta Production: Complexity in Defining
678 Processing Conditions for Reference Trials and Quality Assessment Methods. *CCHEM*,
679 94, 791–797.

680 Nicoletti, I., Martini, D., De Rossi, A., Taddei, F., D'Egidio, M. G., & Corradini, D. (2013).
681 Identification and Quantification of Soluble Free, Soluble Conjugated, and Insoluble
682 Bound Phenolic Acids in Durum Wheat (*Triticum turgidum* L. var. Durum) and Derived
683 Products by RP-HPLC on a Semimicro Separation Scale. *Journal of Agricultural and*
684 *Food Chemistry*, 61(48), 11800–11807. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf403568c>

685 Oliveira, D. G. de, Almeida, C. M. C. de, Silva, C. Y. Y. e, Arruda, M. S. P., Arruda, A. C., Lopes, D.
686 C. F., Yamada, E. S., Costa, E. T. da, M. Filho, A. J., & Silva, M. N. da. (2012). Flavonoids
687 from the leaves of *Deguelia utilis* (Leguminosae): Structural elucidation and

688 neuroprotective properties. *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*, 23, 1933–1939.
689 <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-50532012005000065>

690 Oliver, J., Blakeney, A., & Allen, H. (1992). Measurement of flour color in color space
691 parameters. *Cereal Chemistry*, 69(5), 546–551.

692 Pascual-Teresa, S., Santos-Buelga, C., & Rivas-Gonzalo, J. C. (2002). LC–MS analysis of
693 anthocyanins from purple corn cob. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*,
694 82(9), 1003–1006.

695 Pathare, P. B., Opara, U. L., & Al-Said, F. A.-J. (2013). Colour Measurement and Analysis in
696 Fresh and Processed Foods: A Review. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, 6(1), 36–60.
697 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11947-012-0867-9>

698 Peniche-Pavía, H. A., & Tiessen, A. (2020). Anthocyanin Profiling of Maize Grains Using DIESI-
699 MSQD Reveals That Cyanidin-Based Derivatives Predominate in Purple Corn, whereas
700 Pelargonidin-Based Molecules Occur in Red-Pink Varieties from Mexico. *Journal of*
701 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 68(21), 5980–5994.
702 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b06336>

703 Posit team. (2024). *RStudio: Integrated Development Environment for R* [R]. Posit Software,
704 PBC, Boston, MA. <http://www.posit.co/>

705 R Core Team. (2024). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing* [R]. R
706 Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>

707 Rodriguez, M. D., Monsierra, L., Mansilla, P. S., Pérez, G. T., & de Pascual-Teresa, S. (2024).
708 Phenolic Characterization of a Purple Maize (*Zea mays* cv. “Moragro”) by HPLC–QTOF-
709 MS and Study of Its Bioaccessibility Using a Simulated In Vitro Digestion/Caco-2 Culture
710 Model. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 72(12), 6327–6338.
711 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.3c08960>

712 Rolandelli, G., Farroni, A., & Pilar Buera, M. (2023). Raw Materials. Traditional and Non-
713 conventional Cereals, Pseudo-cereals, Oilseeds and Legumes. In *Designing Gluten Free*
714 *Bakery and Pasta Products* (pp. 19–61). Springer International Publishing.

715 Scarton, M., & Clerici, M. T. P. S. (2022). Gluten-free pastas: Ingredients and processing for
716 technological and nutritional quality improvement. *Food Science and Technology, 42*,
717 e65622. <https://doi.org/10.1590/fst.65622>

718 Silva, E. M. M. da, Ascheri, J. L. R., & Ascheri, D. P. R. (2016). Quality assessment of gluten-free
719 pasta prepared with a brown rice and corn meal blend via thermoplastic extrusion.
720 *LWT - Food Science and Technology, 68*, 698–706.
721 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2015.12.067>

722 Verardo, V., Arráez-Román, D., Segura-Carretero, A., Marconi, E., Fernández-Gutiérrez, A., &
723 Caboni, M. F. (2011). Determination of Free and Bound Phenolic Compounds in
724 Buckwheat Spaghetti by RP-HPLC-ESI-TOF-MS: Effect of Thermal Processing from Farm
725 to Fork. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 59*(14), 7700–7707.
726 <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf201069k>

727 White, M. (2020). *bwsTools: Tools for Case 1 Best-Worst Scaling (MaxDiff) Designs* [R package
728 version 1.2.0]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=bwsTools>

729 Zannini, E., Jones, J. M., Renzetti, S., & Arendt, E. K. (2012). Functional replacements for gluten.
730 *Annual Review of Food Science and Technology, 3*, 227–245.

731 Zou, W., Sissons, M., Warren, F. J., Gidley, M. J., & Gilbert, R. G. (2016). Compact structure and
732 proteins of pasta retard in vitro digestive evolution of branched starch molecular
733 structure. *Carbohydrate Polymers, 152*, 441–449.

734

735

736 **Table 1.** Cooking quality and textural properties of pasta (Mean±SD)

Sample	Moisture (%)	OCT (min)	Water Absorption (%)	Cooking Loss (%)	Swelling Index (%)	Hardness (N)	Cohesiveness	Springiness	Chewiness
Sem	12.48±0.10 ^a	14.42±0.24 ^a	101.08±1.12 ^e	5.80±0.15 ^a	1.51±0.09 ^d	14.00±0.58 ^a	0.590±0.012 ^c	0.932±0.047 ^b	7.69±0.50
Y100	12.63±0.07 ^a	18.33±0.12 ^c	71.59±0.71 ^a	8.87±0.12 ^s	1.11±0.05 ^a	20.50±3.34 ^{ab}	0.379±0.031 ^a	0.998±0.003 ^b	6.99±0.53
Y90	13.13±0.03 ^c	20.25±0.24 ^e	79.55±0.68 ^b	7.22±0.09 ^c	1.23±0.03 ^{ab}	21.80±2.00 ^b	0.418±0.024 ^{ab}	0.742±0.113 ^a	6.66±0.19
P100	12.47±0.02 ^a	16.25±0.35 ^b	83.18±0.47 ^c	6.37±0.18 ^b	1.29±0.06 ^{bc}	18.60±2.31 ^{ab}	0.417±0.043 ^{ab}	0.949±0.050 ^b	7.34±1.99
P90	12.88±0.05 ^b	19.58±0.12 ^d	90.54±0.74 ^d	5.37±0.29 ^a	1.39±0.01 ^{cd}	17.90±5.29 ^{ab}	0.438±0.033 ^b	0.910±0.059 ^b	7.20±2.51

737 There were statistical differences in all properties analysed with the exception of chewiness. For each parameter, different superscript letters indicates statistical
738 difference (p<0.05).

740 **Table 2.** CIELAB colour parameters of pasta (Mean±SD)

Parameter	Sample	Flour Mixture	Dried Pasta	Cooked Dried Pasta
L*	Sem	77.93±0.28 ^{cC}	69.240.44 ^{eA}	73.75±0.14 ^{eB}
	Y100	90.58±0.25 ^{eC}	61.41±0.27 ^{dA}	67.99±0.13 ^{cB}
	Y90	88.86±0.18 ^{dC}	57.63±0.88 ^{cA}	72.01±0.17 ^{dB}
	P100	66.21±0.30 ^{aC}	25.77±0.28 ^{aA}	47.23±0.62 ^{aB}
	P90	68.15±0.15 ^{bC}	29.92±0.94 ^{bA}	52.66±0.75 ^{bB}
a*	Sem	2.80±0.09 ^{cC}	2.36±0.09 ^{aB}	1.17±0.17 ^{aA}
	Y100	0.82±0.05 ^{aA}	11.78±0.23 ^{eC}	6.40±0.41 ^{dB}
	Y90	1.14±0.06 ^{bA}	10.74±0.31 ^{dC}	5.79±0.10 ^{dB}
	P100	7.45±0.06 ^{eC}	5.52±0.05 ^{bB}	3.00±0.10 ^{bA}
	P90	7.06±0.11 ^{dC}	6.26±0.12 ^{cB}	3.66±0.06 ^{cA}
b*	Sem	26.69±0.46 ^{dC}	18.28±0.45 ^{bB}	12.60±0.10 ^{bA}
	Y100	24.55±0.28 ^{bA}	46.01±0.81 ^{cC}	33.01±0.69 ^{cB}
	Y90	25.71±0.17 ^{cA}	51.61±1.03 ^{dC}	36.89±0.90 ^{dB}
	P100	6.10±0.05 ^{aC}	1.17±0.04 ^{aA}	3.99±0.25 ^{aB}
	P90	5.69±0.06 ^{aC}	2.10±0.13 ^{aA}	3.21±0.28 ^{aB}
Chroma	Sem	26.84±0.47 ^{dC}	18.43±0.46 ^{bB}	12.66±0.12 ^{bA}
	Y100	24.57±0.28 ^{bA}	47.50±0.83 ^{cC}	33.63±0.64 ^{cB}
	Y90	25.73±0.17 ^{cA}	52.72±1.07 ^{dC}	37.35±0.89 ^{dB}
	P100	9.63±.08 ^{aC}	5.65±0.04 ^{aB}	5.00±0.22 ^{aA}
	P90	9.07±0.12 ^{aC}	6.60±0.13 ^{aB}	4.87±0.22 ^{aA}
Hue	Sem	84.012±0.128 ^{cB}	82.654±0.106 ^{eA}	84.684±0.726 ^{dB}
	Y100	88.087±0.132 ^{eC}	75.636±0.094 ^{cA}	79.028±0.824 ^{cB}
	Y90	87.453±0.129 ^{dC}	78.246±0.164 ^{dA}	81.073±0.232 ^{cdB}
	P100	39.338±0.06 ^{bB}	11.929±0.505 ^{aA}	53.047±1.799 ^{bC}
	P90	38.884±0.129 ^{aB}	18.514±0.987 ^{bA}	41.221±2.024 ^{aB}

741 For each colour parameter differences in lowercase letters in each column denotes statistical

742 difference between samples (p<0.05). For each colour parameter differences in capital letters in

743 each row denotes statistical difference between processing conditions (p<0.05).

744

745 **Table 3.** Identification of the main compounds in purple corn (P), yellow corn (Y) and semolina (S)

#	Rt (min)	[M-H] ⁺ (m/z)	[M-H] ⁻ (m/z)	MS ions (m/z)	Formula	Identification or possible identification	Occurrence	Reference
1	7,8	265,1573		177,05	C14H20N2O3	Feruloylputrescine	P, Y	pubchem.com
2	8,1	474,1733		327,11; 132,03	C21H29O12	Unknown	S	/
3	8,5	205,0963		146,06	C11H12N2O2	Tryptophan	P, Y, S	Ratha L., et al. (2023)
4	9,5	449,1227		287,05	C21H21O11	Cyanidin 3-glucoside	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
5	10,7	449,1327		287,05	C21H21O11	Cyanidin 3-galactoside	P	Xia Q., et al. (2024)
6	11,3	433,1257		271,07	C21H21O10	Pelargonidin-3-glucoside	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
7	11,7		151,0458	136,11	C8H8O3	Vanillin	S	Dinelli G., et al. (2009)
8	12,4	463,1293		301,07	C22H23O11	Peonidin 3-glucoside	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
9	12,7	493,2775		265,09	C27H40O8	Unknown (putrescine derivative)	P, Y	/
10	12,7	800,2054		287,05; 449,11	No formula	Unknown (cyanidin derivative)	P	/
11	13,6	535,1091		287,05	C24H23O14	Cyanidin 3-malonylglucoside	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
12	13,8		413,1119	206,02	C28H14O4	Unknown	Y	/
13	14,6	800,2054		287,05; 171,62	No formula	Unknown (cyanidin derivative)	P	/
14	14,9	535,1091		287,05	C24H23O14	Cyanidin 3-malonylglucoside	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
15	15,1		593,1709	473,10; 305,84	C27H30O15	Apigenin-6/8-C-pentoside-8/6-C-hexosid	S	Dinelli G., et al. (2009)
16	15,5	163,0408		89,03	C9H6O3	4-hydroxycoumarin	Y	Hu X., et al. (2022)
17	15,6	454,2352		72,08; 220,09; 308,19	C27H33O6	5,3'-dihydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxy-6,8dimethylallyl-flavanone	P, Y	Oliviera D. G. D., et al. (2012)
18	15,7		593,1709	473,10	C27H30O15	Apigenin-6/8-C-pentoside-8/6-C-hexosid	S	Dinelli G., et al. (2009)
19	15,9	454,2352		72,08; 204,10; 292,20	C27H33O6	5,3'-dihydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxy-6,8dimethylallyl-flavanone	P, Y	Oliviera D. G. D., et al. (2012)
20	16,1		179,0407	135,04	C9H8O4	Caffeic acid	P, Y	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
21	16,1	800,2195		287,05; 481,56	No formula	Unknown (cyanidin derivative)	P	/
22	16,4		289,0802	109,02	C15H14O6	Epicatechin	P	pubchem.com
23	16,8	519,1155		271,06	C17H26O18	Pelargonidin-3-(6''malonylglucoside)	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
24	17,1	638,1307		287,05	C28H29O17	Unknown (cyanidin derivative)	P, Y	/

25	17,3	438,2402	204,09; 292,19; 72,08	C25H31N3O4	N,N'-Dicoumaroyl spermidine	P	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
26	17,3	563,1608	443,1	C26H28O14	Schaftoside (apigenin C6 hexose C8 pentose)	S	Dinelli G., et al. (2009)
27	17,7	549,1275	301,06	C25H25O14	Peonidin-3-(6''malonylglucoside)	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
28	17,7	621,1116	287,05	C34H20O12	Cyanidin 3-(dimalonylglucoside)	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
29	17,8	353,0621	127,00	C15H14O10	Unknown	Y	/
30	18,2	292,2035	204,1	C16H25N3O2	N-Coumaroyl spermidine	P	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
31	18,2	438,2402	204,10; 292,20; 72,08	C25H31N3O4	N,N'-Dicoumaroyl spermidine	P, Y	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
32	18,4	563,1608	443,09	C26H28O14	Isoschaftoside (apigenin C6 pentose C8 hexose)	S	Dinelli G., et al. (2009)
33	18,5	621,0866	287,05	C20H28O22	Cyanidin 3-(3'', 6'', dimalonylglucoside)	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
34	18,6	563,1608	443,09	C26H28O14	Isoschaftoside (apigenin C6 pentose C8 hexose)	S	Dinelli G., et al. (2009)
35	18,9	468,2526	177,05; 292,20; 72,08	C26H33N3O5	N,N'-Coumaroyl feruloyl putrescine	P, Y	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
36	19,2	383,0737	127	C16H16O11	Unknown	P	/
37	19,5	498,2761	322,22; 177,05	C27H35N3O6	N,N'-Diferuloylspermidine	P	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
38	19,6	390,1047	228,06	C16H21O11	Unknown	S	/
39	20,2	261,0741	86,26	C14H12O5	Unknown	Y	/
40	20,2	611,1419	287,05; 498,19	C30H26O14	Cyanidin 3-(6-p-caffeoyl) glucoside	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
41	20,8	622,1508	287,05	C28H29O16	Unknown (cyanidin derivative)	P	/
42	21,0	533,1479	289,27; 443,09	C25H26O13	Glycosylated and acetylated 3',4',5'-trihydroxy-3,7-dimethylflavone	S	Dinelli G., et al. (2009)
43	22,1	609,1613	301,03	C34H26O11	Quercetin-3-rutinoside	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)
44	22,1	163,0452	119,05	C9H8O3	p-coumaric acid	P, Y, S	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
45	22,9	625,1558	301,04	C20H34O22	Quercetin diglucoside	P, Y	Chaiittianan R., et al. (2017)
46	23,0	655,1688	287,0506	C21H35O23	Unknown (cyanidin derivative)	P	/
47	23,1	557,1559	206,04; 350,09	C38H22O5	Unknown	P	/
48	24,0	463,1018	301,05	C21H20O12	Quercetin-3-glucoside	P	Rodriguez M. D., et al. (2024)

49	24,3		193,0574	134,03	C10H10O4	Ferulic acid	P, Y, S	Lancheros L. P., et al. (2023)
50	26,3		549,1455	301,04	C24H22O15	Quercetin 3-(6''-malonyl-glucoside)	P	pubchem.com
51	34,2	381,1757		147,04; 235,14	C24O ₂ H ₂₂ N ₅ O ₃	N,N'-dicoumaroyl putrescine	P	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
52	34,4	441,2044		89,10; 177,05; 265,16	C24H28N2O6	N,N'-diferuloyl putrescine	P, Y	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
53	35,1	411,1939		177,05; 265,16	C26H23N3O2	N,N'-coumaroyl feruloyl putrescine	P, Y	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
54	35,9	441,2044		177,05; 265,16	C24H28N2O6	N,N'-diferuloyl putrescine	P	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
55	38,9		301,0465	151	C165H1007	Quercetin	P	Das, A. K., & Singh, V. (2016)
56	40,5	379,2978		361,28	C27H38O	Unknown	S	/
57	40,9	879,3760		439,17; 615,23; 177,05	No formulas	bis-N,N'-diferuloyl putrescine	P	Bento-Silva A., et al. (2020)
58	41,8	427,2813		277,08	C20H42O7S	Unknown	S	/
59	43,8	288,2911		106,08	C17H37NO2	Unknown	P	/

746

747

748 **Table 4:** Quantification of phenolic compounds ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in samples P100 and P90 (Mean \pm SD)

Phenolic Compound	P100					P90				
	F	ND	D	NDC	DC	F	ND	D	NDC	DC
Tryptophan	191,36 \pm 6,16 ^{dB}	237.03 \pm 3.54 ^{aA}	168.26 \pm 3.58 ^{cB}	46.16 \pm 1.42 ^{bA}	51.59 \pm 1.98 ^{bA}	147.50 \pm 7.18 ^{bA}	180.97 \pm 14.28 ^{cB}	151.17 \pm 8.64 ^{bA}	49.73 \pm 0.73 ^{aA}	58.03 \pm 1.98 ^{aB}
Cyanidin 3-glucoside	14,34 \pm 0,90 ^b	11.83 \pm 5.98 ^b	14.92 \pm 0.52 ^b	4.67 \pm 0.38 ^a	2.72 \pm 0.37 ^a	12.12 \pm 0.61 ^b	9.31 \pm 0.74 ^b	9.69 \pm 0.36 ^b	5.40 \pm 0.01 ^a	3.13 \pm 2.72 ^a
Pelargonidin-3-glucoside	1,39 \pm 0,02 ^b	1.17 \pm 1.02 ^a	1.06 \pm 0.07 ^{aB}	0.59 \pm 0.16 ^a	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a	1.30 \pm 0.09 ^c	1.99 \pm 0.20 ^d	1.14 \pm 0.05 ^{aA}	0.84 \pm 0.22 ^b	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Peonidin 3-glucoside	2,23 \pm 0,24 ^b	2.52 \pm 0.49 ^c	3.80 \pm 0.35 ^{dB}	1.06 \pm 0.42 ^a	0.55 \pm 0.50 ^a	2.02 \pm 0.40	1.53 \pm 0.40	1.76 \pm 0.18 ^A	1.03 \pm 0.03	0.98 \pm 0.85
800,2054 [M-H] ⁺ (cyanidin derivative)	2,37 \pm 0,41 ^{bc}	2.72 \pm 0.55 ^{cB}	1.81 \pm 0.30 ^{BB}	0.58 \pm 0.10 ^a	1.23 \pm 0.18 ^a	1.94 \pm 0.31 ^c	1.68 \pm 0.24 ^{cA}	1.20 \pm 0.07 ^{bA}	0.92 \pm 0.16 ^b	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Cyanidin 3-malonylglucoside	1,23 \pm 0,01 ^b	1.46 \pm 0.34 ^b	1.34 \pm 0.17 ^b	0.25 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.18 \pm 0.16 ^a	0.67 \pm 0.15 ^b	0.82 \pm 0.72 ^b	1.23 \pm 0.10 ^b	0.29 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.25 \pm 0.25 ^a
800,2054 [M-H] ⁺ (cyanidin derivative)	1,34 \pm 0,09 ^b	2.21 \pm 0.61 ^c	2.28 \pm 0.19 ^{cB}	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a	1.58 \pm 0.36 ^{bc}	1.27 \pm 0.12 ^b	1.91 \pm 0.06 ^{cA}	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a
Cyanidin 3-malonylglucoside	18,26 \pm 0,96 ^b	15.36 \pm 6.80 ^b	14.04 \pm 0.22 ^b	4.19 \pm 0.36 ^a	3.22 \pm 0.34 ^a	15.55 \pm 1.57 ^b	11.56 \pm 1.15 ^b	11.78 \pm 0.71 ^b	5.67 \pm 0.06 ^a	1.34 \pm 1.16 ^a
Caffeic acid	2,87 \pm 0,24 ^{cB}	0.91 \pm 0.11 ^b	0.56 \pm 0.13 ^{ab}	0.56 \pm 0.08 ^{abB}	0.35 \pm 0.01 ^a	1.33 \pm 0.12 ^{cA}	0.93 \pm 0.10 ^b	0.77 \pm 0.05 ^b	0.35 \pm 0.04 ^{aA}	0.39 \pm 0.06 ^a
Pelargonidin-3-(6''malonylglucoside)	2,43 \pm 0,27 ^b	2.98 \pm 1.39 ^b	3.03 \pm 0.14 ^{BB}	0.65 \pm 0.13 ^a	0.50 \pm 0.45 ^a	2.11 \pm 0.50	1.62 \pm 0.11	1.76 \pm 0.03 ^A	0.65 \pm 0.13	0.50 \pm 0.45
638,13 [M-H] ⁺ (cyanidin derivative)	2,59 \pm 0,27 ^b	3.16 \pm 1.18 ^b	3.17 \pm 0.36 ^{BB}	0.69 \pm 0.14 ^a	0.50 \pm 0.43 ^a	2.29 \pm 0.42	2.06 \pm 0.23	2.00 \pm 0.08 ^A	1.05 \pm 0.17	1.04 \pm 0.90
Cyanidin 3-(dimalonylglucoside)	3,41 \pm 0,56 ^b	3.01 \pm 1.33 ^b	3.54 \pm 0.20 ^{BB}	0.27 \pm 0.24 ^a	0.28 \pm 0.25 ^a	3.83 \pm 0.78 ^c	2.14 \pm 0.21 ^b	2.11 \pm 0.05 ^{bA}	0.87 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.46 \pm 0.41 ^a
N,N'-Dicoumaroyl spermidine	82,01 \pm 5,10 ^{cB}	97.94 \pm 1.37 ^{aA}	92.30 \pm 2.51 ^{dB}	27.80 \pm 5.82 ^b	33.97 \pm 0.57 ^{bA}	56.31 \pm 1.82 ^{cA}	87.64 \pm 2.71 ^{eB}	71.58 \pm 2.96 ^{dA}	30.69 \pm 0.31 ^{aA}	39.39 \pm 0.33 ^{bB}
Cyanidin 3-(3'', 6'', dimalonylglucoside)	4,87 \pm 0,40 ^c	3.70 \pm 1.30 ^b	3.29 \pm 0.25 ^b	0.61 \pm 0.19 ^a	0.30 \pm 0.26 ^a	4.24 \pm 0.79 ^c	2.44 \pm 0.33 ^b	2.17 \pm 0.06 ^b	0.91 \pm 0.03 ^a	0.47 \pm 0.44 ^a
Cyanidin 3-(6-p-caffeoyl)glucoside	0,84 \pm 0,12 ^b	0.98 \pm 0.42 ^b	1.29 \pm 0.11 ^{BB}	0.23 \pm 0.05 ^{aA}	0.16 \pm 0.14 ^a	0.75 \pm 0.18	0.57 \pm 0.09	0.60 \pm 0.05 ^A	0.40 \pm 0.03 ^B	0.37 \pm 0.32
622,1676 [M-H] ⁺ (cyanidin derivative)	1,33 \pm 0,14 ^b	1.40 \pm 0.48 ^b	1.69 \pm 0.08 ^b	0.50 \pm 0.10 ^a	0.36 \pm 0.31 ^a	1.14 \pm 0.06 ^b	1.06 \pm 0.05 ^b	1.06 \pm 0.05 ^b	0.66 \pm 0.06 ^a	0.58 \pm 0.51 ^a

Quercetin-3-rutinoside	1,45±0,07 ^{ba}	1.41±0.15 ^{ba}	1.01±0.43 ^{aA}	0.74±0.04 ^a	0.95±0.19 ^a	2.30±0.32 ^{bb}	1.72±0.10 ^{bb}	1.90±0.35 ^{bb}	0.91±0.11 ^a	0.95±0.20 ^a
Unknown (cyanidin derivative - vitisin like)	1,85±0,21 ^b	1.88±0.45 ^b	2.21±0.24 ^{bb}	0.38±0.35 ^a	0.37±0.32 ^a	1.59±0.42	1.91±0.15	1.15±0.23 ^A	0.48±0.06	0.89±0.78
p-coumaric acid	15,38±0,51 ^{dB}	17.92±0.44 ^{aA}	19.07±0.39 ^{eB}	6.80±0.78 ^b	8.02±0.14 ^{cA}	12.16±0.40 ^{cA}	14.50±0.66 ^{eB}	13.53±0.60 ^{dA}	7.64±0.08 ^a	9.22±0.09 ^{bb}
Quercetin di-glucoside	2,33±0,23 ^{ba}	2.41±0.57 ^{ba}	3.30±0.67 ^b	0.85±0.07 ^a	1.08±0.19 ^a	2.89±0.03 ^{bb}	4.09±0.29 ^{cb}	2.96±0.37 ^b	0.99±0.36 ^a	1.38±0.17 ^a
Quercetin 3-glucoside	2,49±0,21 ^b	3.22±0.12 ^{cb}	2.38±0.34 ^b	0.86±0.07 ^a	0.87±0.10 ^a	2.07±0.03 ^b	2.44±0.07 ^{ba}	2.35±0.35 ^b	0.91±0.14 ^a	0.93±0.04 ^a
Ferulic acid	20,08±0,69 ^d	31.70±0.55 ^{aA}	30.73±0.75 ^{eB}	8.41±1.28 ^b	10.17±0.16 ^{cA}	21.98±1.03 ^c	25.05±0.63 ^{dB}	23.87±0.94 ^{dA}	9.64±0.13 ^a	12.84±0.12 ^b _B
Quercetin-3-O-(6''-O-malonyl)-glucoside	2,18±0,06 ^d	1.77±0.25 ^c	1.01±0.15 ^b	0.34±0.12 ^a	0.76±0.14 ^b	2.27±0.28 ^c	1.67±0.32 ^{bc}	1.25±0.07 ^{ab}	1.13±0.50 ^{ab}	0.61±0.04 ^a
N,N'-Coumaroyl feruloyl putrescine	12,38±1,17 ^c	19.44±0.22 ^{aA}	20.40±0.63 ^{dB}	7.68±0.68 ^b	8.11±0.15 ^{ba}	11.21±0.59 ^b	19.63±0.79 ^{dB}	14.50±0.44 ^{cA}	7.83±0.08 ^a	10.41±0.21 ^b _B
N,N'-Diferuloyl putrescine	40,67±25,15 ^b	47.68±0.58 ^{aA}	59.86±1.79 ^{bb}	14.52±2.84 ^{ab}	16.26±0.05 ^{abA}	24.00±0.83 ^c	53.75±1.48 ^{eB}	38.42±1.63 ^{dA}	15.93±0.06 ^a	21.12±0.23 ^b _B
Quercetin	2,14±0,27 ^b	3.14±0.31 ^{bcB}	3.47±1.06 ^c	0.63±0.09 ^{aA}	0.85±0.14 ^a	1.73±0.24 ^b	1.83±0.17 ^{ba}	2.12±0.18 ^b	0.88±0.04 ^{aB}	0.95±0.34 ^a

749 For each compound (row) and within each sample, differences in lowercase letters denotes statistical difference (p<0.05). For each compound (row) and between
750 each sample for the same processing conditions (e.g.: P100/D vs P90/D), differences in capital letters denotes statistical difference (p<0.05).

751

752 Table 5. Total Polyphenols by FC (mg GAE/g) and antioxidant activity assays (mg TE/g). Mean±SD

Analysis	Sample	F	ND	D	NDC	DC
Folin	Sem	1,26 ± 0,03 ^{bB}	1,53 ± 0,28 ^{cB}	1,15 ± 0,18 ^{cB}	0,10 ± 0,02 ^{aA}	0,11 ± 0,01 ^{aA}
	Y100	0,41 ± 0,05 ^{aC}	0,34 ± 0,06 ^{aBC}	0,30 ± 0,10 ^{aBC}	0,16 ± 0,07 ^{abAB}	0,10 ± 0,01 ^{aA}
	Y90	0,45 ± 0,07 ^{aC}	0,29 ± 0,04 ^{aB}	0,28 ± 0,02 ^{aB}	0,12 ± 0,03 ^{abA}	0,08 ± 0,01 ^{aA}
	P100	1,54 ± 0,09 ^{cC}	1,30 ± 0,07 ^{bCC}	0,95 ± 0,06 ^{bCB}	0,43 ± 0,21 ^{bA}	0,30 ± 0,01 ^{bA}
	P90	1,35 ± 0,11 ^{bCD}	1,11 ± 0,07 ^{bC}	0,86 ± 0,04 ^{bB}	0,40 ± 0,10 ^{abA}	0,41 ± 0,02 ^{CA}
DPPH	Sem	317,08 ± 151,65 ^{aA}	488,63 ± 527,26 ^{aA}	0,00 ± 0,00 ^{aA}	951,78 ± 526,97 ^{aA}	2500,90 ± 207,50 ^{abB}
	Y100	927,47 ± 99,06 ^{bA}	2261,43 ± 308,52 ^{bB}	1030,42 ± 47,75 ^{bA}	709,69 ± 161,51 ^{aA}	2102,35 ± 142,63 ^{abB}
	Y90	920,15 ± 110,94 ^{bA}	1714,31 ± 238,73 ^{bB}	880,09 ± 156,83 ^{bA}	1311,42 ± 303,85 ^{abAB}	2536,35 ± 400,38 ^{abC}
	P100	4493,21 ± 300,80 ^{cC}	6608,88 ± 327,14 ^{cD}	4253,47 ± 279,88 ^{cC}	1249,01 ± 515,16 ^{abA}	2915,18 ± 200,93 ^{bCB}
	P90	4063,48 ± 223,91 ^{cB}	6199,27 ± 489,78 ^{cC}	4088,16 ± 127,79 ^{cB}	2148,38 ± 153,37 ^{bA}	3367,73 ± 239,85 ^{cB}
FRAP	Sem	634,35 ± 123,99 ^{aC}	209,09 ± 97,01 ^{aAB}	436,07 ± 186,59 ^{aBC}	9,24 ± 5,79 ^{aA}	33,05 ± 57,25 ^{aA}
	Y100	1349,69 ± 138,78 ^{bC}	1321,31 ± 96,17 ^{bB}	1002,46 ± 95,99 ^{abB}	505,81 ± 70,61 ^{bA}	249,61 ± 78,91 ^{aA}
	Y90	1045,04 ± 96,25 ^{abB}	1144,45 ± 69,39 ^{bB}	1160,17 ± 188,98 ^{bB}	555,23 ± 97,92 ^{bA}	348,07 ± 30,44 ^{aA}
	P100	5676,70 ± 283,41 ^{dB}	6764,66 ± 138,65 ^{dC}	5288,74 ± 200,24 ^{dB}	1877,27 ± 128,75 ^{cA}	1713,97 ± 67,04 ^{bA}
	P90	5158,99 ± 149,27 ^{cBC}	5543,85 ± 239,47 ^{cC}	4636,88 ± 268,85 ^{cB}	2133,39 ± 78,33 ^{dA}	2083,83 ± 247,41 ^{CA}

753 For each column and assay different lowercase letter denotes statistical difference (p<0.05). For each row different capital letter denotes statistical
754 difference (p<0.05)

755 Table 6. Results from best-worst preference test

Sample	Best	Worst	Best-Worst	Hit Rate	Utility Coefficient (Confidence Interval)	Choice Probability
S	0.677	0.000	0.677	0.839	1.649 (0.972 – 2.325)	63.4%
Y100	0.194	0.097	0.097	0.548	0.194 (-0.306 – 0.694)	14.8%
P100	0.065	0.387	-0.322	0.339	-0.669 (-1.195 – -0.143)	6.2%
Y90	0.032	0.194	-0.162	0.419	-0.325 (-0.830 – 0.179)	8.8%
P90	0.032	0.323	-0.291	0.355	-0.598 (-1.118 – -0.078)	6.7%

756 Best and worst are given in proportions; hit rate and the utility coefficient come from the logit
 757 modelling.

758

759 **Figure Captions**

760 **Figure 1.** Pasta samples images after extrusion (a-e) and after Optimum Cooking Time (f-h). a&f:

761 Sem, b&g:Y100, c:Y90, d&h:P100, e:P90.

762 **Figure 2.** Loading plot from Multiple Factor Analysis of Flash Profiling data

763 **Figure 3.** Correlation plot from Multiple Factor Analysis of Flash Profiling data

764

Individuals - MFA

Quantitative variables - MFA

